

HUMOR AND SATIRE IN SHAKESPEARE'S COMEDIES

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Abstract. Shakespeare is regarded as a brilliant author. His pieces were all well-known and well regarded at the time. Shakespeare's day was not without its inconsistencies, as is evident in all historical eras. Shakespeare, in contrast to other writers, was well aware of the tensions that developed in the complex social structure and personal lives of his times. Unsatisfied with this, he took great care to depict the drama that emerged at these pivotal moments in both society and human existence. In his capacity as a true playwright, he enabled each character to completely defend or explain the abrupt shifts in their conduct by illuminating the social, familial, moral, and spiritual factors that led to this or that action.

Key words: comedy, storyline, sarcasm, satire, historical era social situation.

ЮМОР И САТИРА В КОМЕДИЯХ ШЕКСПИРА

Аннотация. Шекспир считается блестящим автором. Все его произведения в то время были хорошо известны и уважаемы. Во времена Шекспира не обошлось без противоречий, что очевидно во все исторические эпохи. Шекспир, в отличие от других писателей, хорошо осознавал напряженность, возникающую в сложной социальной структуре и личной жизни его времени. Неудовлетворенный этим, он очень тщательно изобразил драму, возникшую в эти переломные моменты как в обществе, так и в человеческом существовании. В качестве настоящего драматурга он позволил каждому персонажу полностью защитить или объяснить резкие изменения в их поведении, освещая социальные, семейные, моральные и духовные факторы, которые привели к тому или иному поступку.

Ключевые слова: комедия, сюжетная линия, сарказм, сатира, социальная ситуация исторической эпохи.

INTRODUCTION

Shakespeare uses a range of humorous techniques in his plays to poke fun at societal conventions, investigate human nature, and amuse viewers. Wordplay is one of the Bard's most common literary devices; examples include puns, double entendres, and astute character dialogue.

This linguistic humor heightens the plays' humorous effect and gives the dialogue more depth. Shakespeare's tragedies have more comedy than his comedies, and that humor matters more.

Shakespeare's interjects comedy when the sorrow gets too much, not just for comedic effect but also to contrast with the severe tragedy that before and will undoubtedly follow.

Shakespeare's comedies are famous for their sharp speech, lighthearted vocabulary, and complex storylines that frequently center on themes of love, misidentification, and societal mores.

In these humorous pieces, the Bard skillfully combines satire and comedy to amuse listeners while providing perceptive comments on social mores and human nature. This article explores how Shakespeare uses sarcasm and comedy to create complex tales, challenge audience preconceptions, and captivate audiences in his comedies. In this play, Shakespeare makes use of the greenworld pattern. The play opens in a metropolis, then travels to a rural area before returning to the city. Shakespeare also frequently uses situational comedy, in which absurdity and hilarity are created via miscommunication, disguise, and mistaken identities. The dramatist questions social norms, displays human arrogance, and exposes human faults via these humorous settings.

HUMOR AND SATIRE IN SHAKESPEARE'S COMEDIES

Comedies of William Shakespeare are well known for their wit, comedy, and social critique. Shakespeare skillfully uses humor to amuse and offer sarcastic insights into human nature and society via the use of puns, wordplay, and exaggerated characters. Shakespeare's comedies contain a variety of humor and sarcasm, which will be explored in this article along with their relevance and effects.¹ Shakespeare's comedies also often include clichés like the conceited authority figure, the lovesick maiden, and the humorous servant. Shakespeare can use comedy and irony to satirically examine gender roles, moral ideals, and societal hierarchy through the use of these classic characters as vehicles.

Shakespeare examines the intricacies of romantic relationships, courting customs, and marriage traditions via satire and comedy. Through the act of defying audience expectations, the Bard asks audiences to consider the nature of human foolishness, love, and desire, all while presenting flawed and humorous characters.

One of the most well-known authors of tragic heroes is William Shakespeare. His plays frequently feature characters who make poor decisions that ultimately bring them to destruction.

¹ Shakespeare, William. *The Complete Works of William Shakespeare**. Edited by Stanley Wells and Gary Taylor. Oxford University Press, 2005.

Shakespeare's most well-known tragic heroes are King Lear, Macbeth, and Hamlet. Tragic heroes are frequently nuanced individuals who are battling inner turmoil. They can be caught between two options, or they might know that what they do could have negative effects, yet they nevertheless feel driven to take action. One of the main elements that makes a tragic hero so likable and interesting is this internal conflict. These people are relatable to us, and their tales serve as a cautionary tale about the perils of human weakness. Prince Hamlet from Shakespeare's play is an example of a tragic hero with hamartia as a defect. The issue with Hamlet is that he overthinks everything and is never able to make a decision, which has terrible results. This terrible weakness may also be found in Romeo and Juliet and Othello.

1. "*The Comedy of Errors*," one of Shakespeare's earliest comedies, is a ridiculous story about misidentified people and misunderstood conversations that end in hilarious mayhem.

Wordplay, puns, and slapstick humor are used throughout the play to illustrate the ridiculousness of human fallibility while also fostering a playful mood.

2. "*A Midsummer Night's Dream*": Shakespeare explores the complexity of love and desire in "*A Midsummer Night's Dream*," a play that combines aspects of comedy, romance, and fantasy. The play parodies the folly of love and the erratic nature of human emotions via the antics of the mischievous Puck and the foolish artisans.

3. The clever comedy "*Much Ado About Nothing*" centers on the wit-war between the sardonic Beatrice and the jaded Benedick. Shakespeare exposes the absurdity of society expectations surrounding love and marriage while infusing the play with humor through deft repartee, sarcasm, and irony.²

Shakespeare's comedies use humor to let audiences laugh at life's inconsistencies and oddities, which gives them a cathartic relief. Laughing explores the absurdities of human nature, which relieves stress and gives a sense of comfort. Shakespeare's comedies employ satire as a means of social criticism, questioning established conventions and drawing attention to the flaws and vices in human nature. Shakespeare uses comedy to highlight the injustice, corruption, and hypocrisy in society. Shakespeare's comic methods have had a lasting impression on Western theater and literature, leaving a cultural legacy. Many playwrights and comedians have been impacted by his use of puns, wordplay, and sarcastic themes, which has helped to shape the evolution of humor as a literary and theatrical art.

² Bergeron, David M. *Shakespeare's Comedies: Solus Rex et Poete**. Routledge, 2002.3. Halio, Jay L. *The Humor of Shakespeare**. University Press of Kentucky, 1995.

CONCLUSION

Shakespeare's comedies are not only more entertaining when humor and sarcasm are present, but they also provide a perceptive reflection on society and human nature. Shakespeare produces comedic plays that both challenge our preconceptions and offer a cathartic release through his deft use of situational comedy, linguistic humor, character humor, and satirical aspects. His comedies still enthrall audiences today, which is evidence of his continuing wit and mastery of satire. Shakespeare's comedies are enhanced by the deft use of humor and satire, which aim to educate, amuse, and provoke viewers. The Bard crafts colorful, complex humorous worlds that speak to timeless themes and universal truths through wordplay, situational comedy, and sarcastic commentary. Viewers may enjoy the humor, wisdom, and revelry that characterize Shakespeare's ongoing contributions to the comedy genre by accepting the comic and satirical qualities of his plays.

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